

TEACHING EXPERIENCE FOR ORGANIZING RESEARCH WORK FOR STUDENTS IN ASTRONOMY

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Abstract. *In this article we propose that an important condition for the successful implementation of scientific astronomical work by schoolchildren is the creative collaboration of an astronomy teacher of a particular school and a university teacher with scientific interests in the field of space exploration. In this case, a wide choice of topics and studies in astronomy opens up, which are characterized as experimental, observational, theoretical or based on numerical and statistical experiments. In our opinion, statistical experiments, including the systematization of known knowledge and the forecast of new astronomical phenomena, are one of the successful areas of organizing at school.*

Key words: *astronomy teacher, secondary school, methodology, Astronomy, general educational subject.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada biz maktab o'quvchilari tomonidan ilmiy astronomik ishlarni muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirishning muhim sharti ma'lum bir maktabning astronomiya o'qituvchisi va koinotni o'rganish sohasida ilmiy qiziqishlari bo'lgan universitet o'qituvchisining ijodiy hamkorligi ekanligini taklif qilamiz. Bunday holda, astronomiyada eksperimental, kuzatuv, nazariy yoki raqamli va statistik tajribalarga asoslangan mavzular va tadqiqotlarning keng tanlovi ochiladi. Bizning fikrimizcha, statistik eksperimentlar, jumladan, ma'lum bilimlarni tizimlashtirish va yangi astronomik hodisalarni bashorat qilish maktabda tashkil etishning muvaffaqiyatli yo'nalishlaridan biridir.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *astronomiya o'qituvchisi, umumta'lim maktabi, metodika, Astronomiya, umumta'lim fani.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье мы предполагаем, что важным условием успешного выполнения школьниками научной астрономической работы является творческое сотрудничество учителя астрономии конкретной школы и преподавателя вуза, имеющего научные интересы в области изучения космоса. В этом случае открывается широкий выбор тем и исследований по астрономии, которые характеризуются как экспериментальные, наблюдательные, теоретические или основанные на численных и статистических экспериментах. По нашему мнению, статистические эксперименты, включающие систематизацию известных знаний и прогнозирование новых астрономических явлений, являются одним из успешных направлений организации в школе.*

Ключевые слова: *учитель астрономии, средняя школа, методика, астрономия, общеобразовательный предмет.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern Astronomy is the most important source of knowledge about the world around us, the basis of scientific and technological progress and at the same time one of the most important components of human culture. As a subject of the secondary school curriculum, it allows equipping students with the basics of Astronomy - the science of nature. The content, system and methodology of Astronomy opens up great opportunities for the formation of a scientific worldview of students, the development of practical skills and abilities, effective skills of

independent work. When implementing assignments in Astronomy, students' mental abilities are developed, in particular logical thinking, as a reflection of higher logic - the logic of nature [1]. The study of Astronomy as a general educational subject at school is important in preparing students for life in the modern world of technology, as well as in the formation of their general worldview.

The concept of teaching the subject "Astronomy" in educational organizations implementing basic general educational programs defines the main goals of studying Astronomy in an educational organization:

- developing students' interest and desire for the scientific study of nature, developing their intellectual and creative abilities;
 - development of ideas about the scientific method of cognition and the formation of a research attitude towards surrounding phenomena;
 - the formation of a scientific worldview as a result of studying the foundations of the structure of matter and the fundamental laws of Astronomy;
 - development of skills to explain phenomena using physical knowledge and scientific evidence;
 - formation of ideas about the role of Astronomy for the development of other natural sciences, engineering and technology;
- development of ideas about possible areas of future professional activity related to Astronomy, preparation for further education in this direction [2-4].

At present, due to ground observations and research conducted using spacecraft and artificial satellites of the Earth and planets, significant scientific information about the Solar system, the Galaxy, and the Metagalaxy has been collected. At the same time, the volume of experimental data is growing rapidly, which urgently leads to the need to develop synthesizing theories that take into account new facts and interpret large volumes of information in a condensed form. Thus, in the modern era, which requires new ideas for the effective solution of problems posed to astronomy, there is an acute need for researchers who are able to take an unconventional approach to finding answers to relevant questions. For example, in the problem of the formation and stability of the Solar system, the main and unsolved problems are considered to be: the origin and evolution of the Moon, the distribution of planetary satellites and asteroids, the origin and nature of planetary rings, the distribution of cometary orbits and matter, the evolution of rotational motion, resonances in the orbital-rotational motion of celestial bodies. On the other hand, the small number of hours devoted to the study of astronomy in secondary schools forces astronomy teachers to seek new forms of teaching, considering students not only as accumulators of known knowledge, but also as producers of new natural scientific knowledge about the astronomical Universe.

The need and urgency of training talented young people as future research scientists is indicated by new forms of involving secondary school students in scientific activities. In addition to the traditionally and regularly held Olympiads in astronomy and space Astronomy, there is the "Discovery" program, within the framework of which there is a sub-seminar "Astronomy", and an annual scientific conference for schoolchildren. The "Star" magazine informs astronomy enthusiasts about upcoming international conferences, where representatives of secondary educational institutions can present reports on the topics of their scientific developments. According to the authors of this article, the best conditions for organizing the educational process in astronomy with elements of independently conducted scientific research are formed in schools for the following reasons. These educational institutions are attended by

children who have determined the area of their interests, at least in academic subjects, and, in particular, are interested in astronomy. There are IBM PC386 computer classes and, consequently, the possibility of conducting mass numerical experiments [5].

In addition, access to databases about the Universe via e-mail allows you to quickly receive and process relevant information. An important condition for the successful implementation of scientific astronomical work by schoolchildren is the creative collaboration of an astronomy teacher of a particular school and a university teacher with scientific interests in the field of space exploration. In this case, a wide choice of topics and studies in astronomy opens up, which are characterized as experimental, observational, theoretical or based on numerical and statistical experiments. In our opinion, statistical experiments, including the systematization of known knowledge and the forecast of new astronomical phenomena, are one of the successful areas of organizing at school. We also note such a form of scientific work as conducting scientific observations at astronomical observatories. Search for comets and asteroids, lunar occultation's of stars, detection of unknown space objects, study of variable stars, study of the physical nature of planets. We emphasize that it is useful to obtaining scientific knowledge and significant original information about the world around us, and not just simple reproduction of knowledge [6]. When a university lecturer and an astronomy teacher manage to awaken the creative powers of a schoolchild, the results of his scientific research can be presented not only at school and university conferences, but also at all- international scientific conferences devoted to astronomical problems. It is not excluded that the results will be published in the leading astronomical journal, the *Astronomical Journal*.

In this educational institution, astronomy was studied in two eleventh grades only in the second half of the academic year. In the "natural sciences" class, unlike the "humanities" class, along with the general astronomy course for all students, topics for individual creative work from various sections of astronomy were offered. Students were presented with an unsolved problem of modern astronomy and were required to find, at least in the initial approximation, an original solution to it. In the process of solving the creative problem, the level of development of the cognitive abilities of students was taken into account [4], who carried out astronomical observations, numerical experiments on a computer, theoretical studies of the Solar System, our Galaxy, and the Metagalaxy.

1. Establishing a pattern between the sizes of planetary satellites and the distance of satellites to the planets.
2. Determining the number of planetary satellites based on known parameters of the planets.
3. Calculation of solar sail parameters for a flight to Mars.
4. Estimation of the number of planets that may be forming near the star (3 Pictoris).
5. Development of methods for determining the mass of the Galaxy.
6. Calculation of the flight time to Mars and back along orbits with the least energy expenditure.
7. Development of methods for determining the distance to an artificial Earth satellite in the event of its crossing the planet based on the results of angular measurements.
8. Establishing a connection between the temperature on the surface of the planets and their distance from the Sun.
9. Determination of the shape of the nuclei and spiral arms of galaxies.
10. "Gravitational atom" and its properties.
11. Forecast of approaches of bodies of the Solar System.

In the future, this work on organizing research is expected to continue, especially since we have developed a program and compiled a curriculum for studying astronomy, where the number of study hours is three times greater than usual. The central point of the program is individual creative work, including scientific research, of school students in astronomy.

CONCLUSION

The authors of the article believe that the main role of the teacher in organizing the scientific research work of schoolchildren is reduced not only to modeling educational problems, but also, most importantly, to the acquisition of new original knowledge by the students themselves. This position differs significantly from the judgments expressed in the works. We note such a form of scientific work as conducting scientific observations at astronomical observatories. Search for comets and asteroids, lunar occultation's of stars, detection of unknown space objects, study of variable stars, study of the physical nature of planets. We emphasize that it is useful to obtaining scientific knowledge and significant original information about the world around us, and not just simple reproduction of knowledge [6].

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